

Contribution of rural women to their household food utilization

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study were to determine the contribution of RDRS women beneficiaries to their household food utilization and to explore its relationship with their selected characteristics. The study was conducted at Sadar upazila of Panchagarh district. Ninety-four RDRS women beneficiaries were selected randomly as a sample from 935 women beneficiaries. A pre-tested interview schedule was used to collect data from the respondents from 24 September to 22 October 2019. The contribution of women beneficiaries to household food utilization was considered as the focus issue of the study and measured by a 4-point rating scale along with five dimensions containing twenty-six activities. The observed overall contribution of women beneficiaries score ranged from 16 to 74 with a mean of 38.21 and standard deviation of 13.43. The RDRS women beneficiaries played medium to high contributions to household food utilization. Among different dimensions of food utilization, the most important contribution was food preparation, followed by food hygiene and intra-household food distribution. Correlation analysis indicated that educational qualification, earning members, credit received and extension media contact were positively correlated with the contribution to their household food utilization and negatively correlated with household annual income and dependency ratio. It may be recommended that, RDRS should provide sufficient non-formal education like training, extension campaigns, discussions with their women beneficiaries regarding household food utilization. In this connection special emphasis need to be given on “food processing and preservation” as well as “water and sanitation” dimensions of food utilization for improving beneficiaries’ knowledge on household food utilization.

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Introduction

Food security is the physical and economic access to sufficient food to meet the dietary requirements for productive and healthy life (FAO, 2007). Peoples’ food security occurs when

all have physical and economic availability and access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food at all times that meet their dietary needs and food preferences for active and healthy life (IFPRI, 2021). Four main dimensions of food security

can be identified as physical availability of food, economic and physical access to food, food utilization, and stability of the other three dimensions over time (FAO, 2008). In contrast to the other three pillars food utilization is often used interchangeably with nutrition, yet while utilization focuses on nutrition; it also includes food storage, processing, health, and sanitation as they relate to nutrition (Aromolran *et al.*, 2017). Thus, food utilization refers to the way that households' used to meet specific dietary and nutritional needs, as well as individuals' ability to absorb the nutrients. It is exhaustively linked with the betterment of the livelihood of the farm people (Hanif *et al.*, 2018). It includes a variety of issues, such as food storage/processing, intra-household food distribution, preparation practices, infant and young child feeding practices, hygiene practices, and access to safe water and sanitation.

Rural women play an essential role in the four pillars of food security. Women are generally responsible for food selection and preparation and the care and feeding of the family. They are the key to food security for their household food utilization (ADB, 2013). Their role in food utilization for food security is perhaps the most critical and outweighs the importance of their role in food production and how they spend the income they earn. They are typically responsible for food preparation and thus are crucial to the dietary diversity of their households. Therefore, they play a decisive role in food security, dietary diversity, and children's health (Nasrin, 2015). They have to play both productive and reproductive roles in other words both maintaining the household and securing foodstuff for the household members.

Rangpur Dinajpur Rural Service (RDRS) is one of the leading non-governmental organization (NGO) in the northwest of the Bangladesh working with the disadvantaged people in order to build their empowerment capacity, create resilience to adverse situation and improve access to opportunities to realize decent lives free from poverty and distress (Islam, 2010). The organization is a break through with a view to bringing rural women

to improve their efficiency in household activities and to make them conscious about household health and nutrition. As rural women are the main organizer of household-related activities, they are often faced with a variety of obstacles which render them unable to fulfil their role as gatekeepers by dedicating their own time, income and decision-making to maintain food and nutritional security of their households and communities. These obstacles might vary with the socio-economic scenario of the rural women. To determine the food security status we need to consider women contribution to their household food utilization along with their socio-economic characteristics. It was expected that contribution of the women towards food utilization would be influenced by the selected characteristics of the respondents. Thus, we considered some selected characteristics of the women beneficiaries to measure their relationship with household food utilization.

Objectives of the Study

The present study was undertaken with the following specific objectives:

- a. to determine the contribution of RDRS women beneficiaries to their household food utilization; and
- b. to explore the relationship between the contribution of women beneficiaries to their household food utilization and their selected characteristics.

Materials and Methods

Research design: An ex-post-facto explanatory cross-sectional research design (Hasan *et al.*, 2018) was used for this study as the study is quasi-experimental in nature and it tried to predict the relationship of the selected characteristics of the female beneficiaries with their contribution to food utilization at a particular time. The face-to-face interview method was used for data collection. A pre-tested interview schedule was used during the interview for data collection. The interview schedule contained both open and closed form questions. Data were collected from 24 September to 22 October 2019.

Study area: The study was conducted in the

Panchagarh district. This is the northernmost district of Bangladesh and is considered as one of the most high prevalence food-insecure districts of the north-west zone (Coirolo *et al.*, 2013). The researchers are familiar with the socio-cultural environment of the district.

The Sadar Upazila of Panchagarh district was selected randomly among the five Upazilas of the district. Thus, the Sadar Upazila of Panchagarh was the locale of the study.

Sampling Design: RDRS was selected purposively for data collection as it is one of the top-ranked NGOs working in Sadar Upazila of Panchagarh district. The women beneficiaries who are the members of RDRS of the Panchagarh Sadar Upazila for at least last two years constitute the population of the study and the total number was 935. Due to constraints of time and resources, 10 percent of the population that is 94 women beneficiaries were randomly selected as a sample by using a simple random sampling method for data collection. The random sampling method is selected as it eliminates bias by giving all individuals an equal chance to be chosen in the sampling frame (Hasan *et al.*, 2018). A reserve list of 10 women beneficiaries was also prepared for using as a sample in case of unavailability of original sampled women during the interview.

Variables of the study: Twelve characteristics of the RDRS women beneficiaries viz., age, educational qualification, household size, household farm size, household annual income, earning members, dependency ratio, training experience, credit received, extension media contact, access to facilities and family shock faced were selected based on review of literature and previous similar studies. The measurement of these variables are given below. Age of the respondents were measured in terms of the actual years passed from her birth to the day of interview (Sultana, 2017). The educational qualification was measured on the basis of grade passed by a respondent from a formal institution or equivalent qualification possessed (Sarmin & Hasan, 2019). Household size is the total number of family member (Hasan *et al.*, 2019),

whereas household farm size referred to the total area of land on which the respondent's family carried out farming operation (Mondol, 2019). Household annual income was considered as the total income obtained from different sources by all the members of the household of the respondent (Hasan *et al.*, 2019). The earning member indicates the total number of family member(s) of the household involved in earning (Sultana, 2017). The dependency ratio of a respondent's household was measured by ratio of total dependent members (number of children aged under 15 years and number of the older aged above 65 years) to total working members (number of members aged 15 to 65) of the household, multiplied by 100 (Sultana, 2017). Training received was considered as the participation of the respondents in different training activities in her life expressed in days (Hasan *et al.*, 2019). Credit received was measured in terms of the amount of money received by the respondent from different monetary organizations (Sultana, 2017; Mondol, 2019). For measuring the extension media contact a four-point rating scale was used along with selected 14 extension media contact with the extent of responses of 'regularly', 'often', 'rarely, and 'not at all' with score values of 3, 2, 1 and 0, respectively. Thus, the total extension media contact score of a respondent could vary from 0 to 42, where 0 indicating no extension media contact and 42 indicating highest level of extension media contact (Kisku, 2017). Access to different facilities was measured by nine facilities accessible by the respondent. Each facility has a binary responses such as 'yes' or 'no' with a scoring of 1 and 0, respectively (Sultana, 2017; Mondol, 2019). Family shock faced by the respondents was measured by statements related to six shocks faced by the respondents like domestic or physical violence, dowry demand, death of child before five years etc.. Each of the statement has binary responses such as 'yes' or 'no' with a scoring of 1 and 0, respectively (Sultana, 2017; Mondol, 2019). The focus issue of the study was the contribution of women beneficiaries to their household food utilization.

Measurement of the focus issue: Food

utilization is an important pillar among the four pillars of food security which addresses not only how much food the people eat but also what and how they eat and is comprehensively linked with poverty (Islam *et al.*, 2007). In this study, we considered four dimensions of food utilization as suggested by Nasrin (2015) viz. food preparation, food processing and preservation, water and sanitation and intra-household food distribution. In addition, we also considered food hygiene as a dimension of food utilization as it helps to protect the health of consumers from foodborne illness and food poisoning (Ehuwa *et al.*, 2021). Twenty-six activities of five dimensions to household food utilization namely, food preparation (four activities), food processing and preservation (six activities), food hygiene (five activities), water and sanitation (five activities) and intra-household food distribution (six activities) were considered for measurement of 'contribution in household food utilization'. These activities were measured by a 4-point rating scale following the methodology of Nasrin (2015). The score was assigned as '0' for not at all, '1' for low, '2' for medium and '3' for high contribution to the activities related to household food utilization. Thus, a total score of a respondent might vary from 0 to 78 on this scale, where '0' indicated not at all and '78' indicated the highest contribution to the activities related to household food utilization.

Ranking of the dimensions of contribution to household food utilization

To rank the selected five dimensions, contribution index (CI) along with rank order was computed by using the following formula:

Mean contribution index of a specific dimension (MCI) = Mean of (Sum of a total score of all

the activities of the specific dimension/Number of total activities of the specific dimension)

The MCI score could range from 0 to 3, where 0 indicates no contribution at all to that specific dimension and 3 indicates the highest extent of contribution to that specific dimension.

Data analysis: The collected data were coded, compiled, tabulated and analyzed. The local units were converted into standard units. The qualitative data were transferred into quantitative data by appropriate scoring techniques. Data were analyzed following the objectives of the study by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer program (version 23). Various statistical measures such as range, mean, number, percentage, standard deviation and rank order were used to describe the selected characteristics of the respondents of the study area. To find out the relationship between the selected characteristics of the farmers and their household food utilization, Karl Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was computed.

Result and Discussions

Contribution of RDRS women beneficiaries to their household food utilization

The observed overall contribution of women beneficiaries to their household food utilization score ranged from 16 to 74 with the possible range of 0 to 78 Table 1. The mean score of the contribution of women beneficiaries to their household food utilization is 38.21 with a standard deviation of 13.43. Based on mean and standard deviation of the contribution to household food utilization score (mean±standard deviation), the women beneficiaries were classified into three categories are presented in Table 1.

The findings implied that the majority of the respondents were clustered around the moderate

Table 1. Distribution of women beneficiaries according to their contribution to household food utilization score (N=94).

Categories	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Std. deviation
Low (≤26)	8	8.5		
Moderate (27-52)	74	78.7	38.21	13.43
High (above 52)	12	12.8		
Total=	94	100.0		

contribution to high contribution to their food utilization category. This is in support of the findings of Kobir (2007), Rahman (2010) and Nasrin (2015). Household food utilization is an important pillar for the assurance of household food security. As it was found that women beneficiaries had moderate to high food utilization, their knowledge and skill on the same can be further strengthened for ensuring food security and assuring adequate food utilization in their households. In addition, women had low contribution to their household food utilization need to focus intensively for ensuring household food security. This can be done by different non-formal education like training, group discussion etc.

The rank order of the dimensions of contribution to household food utilization

The contribution of RDRS women beneficiaries towards household food utilization has been examined by computing rank order through the mean contribution index of the women are shown in Table 2.

The findings of Table 2. show that the mean Contribution Indices (CI) of the selected five dimensions of contribution to household food utilization ranged from 1.09 to 1.67 against a possible range of 0 to 3. Dimension wise rank order of the contribution to the household food utilization indicates that food preparation dimension ranked top followed by food hygiene and intra-household food distribution. The degree of variation is comparatively low for these dimensions also. But the women beneficiaries had less contribution to water and sanitation and least contribution to food processing and preservation.

Their degree of variation is also comparatively high for these two dimensions indicating the distribution is disperse highly around the mean. Lack of proper sanitation awareness might be the root cause for such findings. In addition, households having solvency in income might employ helping hands who are basically responsible for food processing and preservation other than the respondents themselves. In addition, these households might be highly dependent on processed foods available in market. But these two dimensions are very much important for the management of household health and nutrition. Thus, women beneficiary's knowledge and skill on these two dimensions are needed to be improved for increasing their contribution. This might improve their insight and might contribute more to their household food utilization.

Characteristics profile of the women beneficiaries

There were various characteristics of the women beneficiaries that might influence their contribution to their household food utilization. In the present study, twelve characteristics of the RDRS women beneficiaries were selected, which included their age, educational qualification, household size, household farm size, household annual income, earning member, dependency ratio, training experience, credit received, extension media contact, access to facilities and family shock faced. The salient features of the characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 3.

Findings of Table 3 indicated that an overwhelming majority of the respondents were middle to young. Exposure to formal education is very

Table 2. Rank order of the dimensions of the contribution of women beneficiaries to their household food utilization.

Dimensions	Contribution index		
	Mean	CV	Rank
1. Food preparation	1.67	34.78	1st
2. Food processing and preservation	1.09	56.87	5th
3. Food Hygiene	1.64	33.30	2nd
4. Water and sanitation	1.36	44.33	4th
5. Intra-household food distribution	1.51	36.43	3rd

CV = Coefficient of variation

Table 3. Distribution of the women beneficiaries based on their selected characteristics scores (N=94).

Characteristics	Scoring method	Range		Categories	Respondents		Mean	SD
		Possible score	Observed		Freq.	%		
Age	No. of year	Unknown	22-60	Young (18-35)	30	31.9	40.26	9.28
				Middle (36-55)	59	62.8		
				Old (> 55)	5	5.3		
Educational qualification	Year of schooling	Unknown	0.5-16	Can sign name only (0.5)	51	54.3	4.17	4.60
				Primary (1-5)	10	10.6		
				Secondary (6-10)	25	26.6		
				Higher secondary (11-12)	4	4.3		
				Above higher secondary (>12)	4	4.3		
Household size	No. of members	Unknown	3-9	Small (1-4)	45	47.9	4.79	1.30
				Medium (5-6)	39	41.5		
				Large (>6)	10	10.6		
Household farm size	Hectare	Unknown	0.17-2.77	Marginal (<0.21)	21	22.3	0.45	0.39
				Small (0.21-1.0)	68	72.3		
				Medium (1.01-3.0)	5	5.3		
Household annual income	('000'Tk.)	Unknown	91-530	Low (\leq 100.00)	6	6.4	172.35	68.29
				Medium (100.01-200.00)	69	73.4		
				High (200.01-300.00)	15	16.0		
				Very high (>300.00)	4	4.3		
Earning member	No. of members	Unknown	1-7	Low (1-2)	19	20.2	3.69	1.32
				Moderate (3-4)	51	54.3		
				High (>4)	24	25.5		
Dependency ratio	Score	0-100	0-83.33	No dependency (0)	32	34.0	21.73	21.15
				Low dependency (1-33.00)	35	37.2		
				Moderate dependency (33.01 to 66.00)	20	21.3		
				High dependency (above 66.00)	7	7.4		
Training experience	Day	Unknown	1-6	Daylong (1)	58	61.7	1.69	1.8
				Two-days (2)	27	28.7		
				Above two-days (>2)	9	9.6		
Credit received	('000'Tk.)	Unknown	0-270	No (0)	22	23.4	40.16	57.25
				Low (1 to 90.00)	59	62.8		
				Medium (90.01-180.00)	7	7.4		
				High (>180.00)	6	6.4		
Extension media contact	Score	0-42	7-34	Low (1 to 14)	23	24.5	19.05	6.23
				Medium (15-28)	60	63.8		
				High (>28)	11	11.7		
Access to facilities	Score	0-9	2-8	Low (\leq 3)	16	17.0	4.67	1.25
				Medium (4-6)	70	74.5		
				High (>6)	8	8.5		
Family shock faced	Score	0-6	1-6	Low (\leq 2)	63	67.0	2.31	1.26
				Medium (3-4)	23	24.5		
				High (>4)	8	8.5		

important for shaping up the behaviour of an individual. It was found that respondents having higher education (above secondary level) are very few in number and most of the respondents are dropped out from education after their secondary level. However, more than half of the respondents have no formal institutional education in the study area. It was found that 89.4 percent of the respondents had small to medium sized household. It is assumed that the respondents having small and medium household are likely to provide more contribution to their household food utilization especially considering the dimension intra-household food distribution. Following the classification of DAE (2016) it was found that the majority of the respondents had small to marginal sized farm and there were no landless and large farm sized women beneficiaries. RDRS mainly work with the disadvantageous group of people, thus the large farm sized respondents were absent, whereas the landless respondents were absent as most of them maintain their livelihood by selling their labor to other households and they were highly dependent on those households for food utilization.

Results presented in Table 3 show that majority of the respondents had medium to high income, whereas about four-fifth of the respondents had moderate to high earning members in their household. Earning member expresses how many household members are earning and higher-earning member of the household indicates that more earning of the household. The results indicates that 49 households having 4+ family members and out of these 24 have 4+ earning members. This indicates that, households having more family members are less engaged in earning. The dependency ratio expresses how many non-earning aged family members are dependent on an earning aged member and higher dependency ratio of the household indicates that more non-earning aged household members is dependent on less earning aged member of the household. It was found that about one-third of the respondents had no dependency that is all the members of their family were earning aged members. Results also indicates that, high dependency is not profuse in the study area.

The training experience of the women beneficiaries is directly related to their organizational affiliation as well as skill development. The range of duration of training experience was very narrow but the respondents were mainly clustered in “daylong training” and “two-day training” categories. As training improves psychomotor as well as cognitive contents of an individual, women contribution to food utilization can further be improved by training programs. It was found that majority of the respondents clustered around no to low credit received categories. The socio-cultural barrier as well as male dominance in the family might influence this kind of findings. A overwhelming majority of the respondents (88.3 percent) had low to medium extension media contact in the study area which was an indication of inadequate extension services to their community.

Access to facilities might indicate the inherent strength of a respondent to contribute more to their household food utilization. The findings show that most of the respondents had low to medium access to facilities which was an indication of their medium contribution to their household food utilization. Family shock is the dummy psychological stress variable of the respondents which might inversely affect to the contribution to household food utilization. It was also found that overwhelming majority (91.5 percent) of the respondents had low to medium family shock faced in the study area. These issues might be considered for improvement of the women's contribution towards household food utilization.

Relationship between the selected characteristics of RDRS women beneficiaries and their contribution in household food utilization

Karl Pearson's Product Moment Correlation co-efficient (r) was used to determine the relationships between the selected characteristics and the focus issue. A summary of the correlation analysis is presented in Table 4.

Out of twelve selected characteristics of the women beneficiaries four namely, educational qualification, earning members, credit received

Table 4. Relationships between the selected characteristics of the women beneficiaries and their contribution to household food utilization.

Focus issue	Selected characteristics	Computed values of 'r' with 92 df.	Tabulated value of 'r'	
			0.05 level	0.01 level
Contribution to household food utilization	Age	0.092		
	Educational qualification	0.498**		
	Household size	0.018		
	Household farm size	0.140		
	Household annual income	-0.235*		
	Earning members	0.314**	±0.203	±0.265
	Dependency ratio	-0.334**		
	Training experience	0.140		
	Credit received	0.254*		
	Extension media contact	0.342**		
	Access to facilities	-0.094		
	Family shock faced	0.064		

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level and ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

and extension media contact showed positive significant relationship with their contribution to household food utilization. In contrast, household annual income and dependency ratio of the women beneficiaries showed negative significant relationship with their contribution to household food utilization. Rests of the characteristics such as age, household size, household farm size, training experience, access to facilities and family shock faced by the women beneficiaries had no significant relationship with their contribution to household food utilization. Educational qualification of an individual might expand the horizon of outlook and insight of a respondent (Sarmin and Hasan, 2019). This might help them to contribute more to their household food utilization. Having more earning members in a household might open up the communication opportunities with the outside world and the respondents of such households might get more information in this indirect pathway which might improve their knowledge on food utilization. Similarly, to receive credit the respondents might require functional interpersonal communication with the credit providing institutions. This might improve their cognitive ability which might help their analytical potential for improving their contribution to household

food utilization. More contribution to household food utilization as extension media contact is a kind of non-formal education which improves the cognitive ability of the respondents (Kisku, 2017) which ultimately helps respondents to contribute more to their household food utilization. However, respondents having high household annual income had less contribution to household food utilization. This might be due to the fact that, high income households had more helping hands in their households who deal the food related issues. In addition, these households might be highly dependent on processed foods which are easily available in market. Dependency ratio also has negative relationship with contribution to household food utilization which might be due to the fact that households having high dependency ratio are more concerned about the availability and access of food rather than utilization.

Conclusions

The majority of the RDRS women beneficiaries had a medium extent of contribution to their household food utilization indicating there is plenty of opportunities to improve their contribution to household food utilization. In addition, the positive correlation between the extension media contact and the focus issue indicates that

different non-formal educational activities like training, extension campaigns, discussions are needed to be emphasized to improve women beneficiaries' contribution to food utilization, more specifically on "food processing and preservation" and "water and sanitation" dimensions. In this connection, the non-formal educational activities should focus on the need of rural women for increasing their awareness, management skill and operational abilities to contribute more to their household food utilization. Moreover, the educational qualification is positively related with contribution to household food utilization indicating government should bring more rural women under educational facilities by strengthening the whole system. Access to credit facilities are needed to be boosted-up with easy terms and conditions for the rural women. Proper initiatives should be taken to create diversified income-generating activities so that rural women would engage themselves in such activities to increase their income and play an important contribution to their household food utilization in one hand. On the other hand, they should also be motivated for their proper roles in food utilization and thereby improving the food security situation of their households. In addition, awareness programs should be taken in the study area for increasing women's access to control over resources as well as their contribution in household decision-making process.

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